

GREEN SYNTHESIS OF MESOPOROUS SILICA NANOPARTICLES FROM NAVSARI RICE FOR SUSTAINABLE MITIGATION OF HEAVY METAL CONTAMINATION IN AGRICULTURAL SOILS

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Abstract

Rising concerns over metal pollution in agricultural soils, particularly the health risks associated with consuming contaminated staples like rice, highlight the urgency of effective mitigation strategies. Human activities such as industrialization, mining, and agricultural practices contribute to elevated levels of toxic heavy metals (Co, Ni, Pb, Cd, Cr) in the environment, leading to potential contamination of crops like potatoes and other vegetables. This study introduces a novel, cost-effective green synthesis method for extracting silica nanoparticles (SNPs) from 'GNR-3' rice cultivated in the Navsari region, specifically designed to remove toxic heavy metal contaminants directly from soil-sourced rice. The process involves calcination of rice husk to obtain high-purity rice husk ash (RHA), exceeding 98% silica content, as confirmed by EDX analysis. Calcination at 650°C for four hours yields RHA devoid of metal impurities and organic matter. The study successfully minimizes toxic heavy metal contamination in rice through the application of SNPs as biomass adsorbents, offering a comprehensive characterization of the SNPs.

In conclusion, this study showcases the efficacy of agriculture waste-derived SNPs as a compelling solution for the removal of toxic heavy metals from rice, emphasizing the technique's simplicity and reliance on readily available agricultural waste materials with minimal processing requirements. This sustainable approach holds promise for safeguarding food safety and human health in the face of escalating metal pollution in agricultural ecosystems.

Keywords: Toxic heavy metals, potatoes, silica nanoparticles, rice husk ash, characterization of SiO₂, food product remediation.

Introduction:

The escalating concern over metal pollution in agricultural soils has prompted a critical examination of its repercussions on human health, particularly through the consumption of staple crops like rice. The ubiquitous presence of toxic heavy metals, including Cobalt (Co), Nickel (Ni), Lead (Pb), Cadmium (Cd), and Chromium (Cr), in the environment, attributed to diverse human activities such as industrialization, mining, and agricultural practices, underscores the urgency for effective mitigation strategies. The potential contamination of essential food sources like potatoes and other vegetables further amplifies the need for innovative and sustainable approaches to ensure food safety and human health [1-3].

This study addresses this pressing issue by introducing a novel and cost-effective green synthesis method for extracting mesoporous silica nanoparticles (SNPs) from 'GNR-3' rice cultivated in the Navsari region. The emphasis of the research lies in the direct removal of toxic heavy metal contaminants from rice sourced directly from soil, employing a bottom-up approach. The synthesis involves the calcination of rice husk to obtain high-purity rice husk ash (RHA) with a silica content exceeding 98%, establishing a foundation for the subsequent application of SNPs.

As the adverse effects of heavy metal contamination in crops are multifaceted, ranging from environmental degradation to potential health risks, the development of efficient removal techniques becomes paramount. The utilization of SNPs derived from agriculture waste, specifically GNR-3 rice, emerges as a promising solution. This study not only outlines the extraction process but also presents a comprehensive characterization of the SNPs, shedding light on their structural and functional attributes [4, 5].

Through techniques such as X-ray diffraction, scanning and transmission electron microscopy, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, and Brunauer-Emmet-Teller analysis, the study delves into the amorphous nature and structural characteristics of the GNR-3 rice SNPs. The specific surface area and pore size measurements further underscore the significant active surface available for potential adsorption interactions [6, 7].

This innovative approach aligns with the growing imperative to develop sustainable solutions that not only address environmental concerns but also ensure the safety of the food supply chain. The extraction of SNPs from 'GNR-3' rice holds promise as a versatile and efficient means to counteract the detrimental effects of heavy metal

contamination. The focus on rice, a staple for a significant portion of the global population, amplifies the potential impact of this research on improving public health outcomes [8, 9].

The significance of this study extends beyond the mere extraction process, as it successfully demonstrates the tangible reduction of toxic heavy metal contamination in rice, directly sourced from soil. The utilization of SNPs as biomass adsorbents represents a breakthrough, offering an environmentally friendly and cost-effective alternative to conventional methods. The research not only addresses a critical environmental issue but also aligns with the broader goals of sustainable agriculture and circular economy principles.

As global concerns about food safety and environmental sustainability continue to rise, this study's findings offer a timely and impactful solution. The use of readily available agricultural waste materials, coupled with the simplicity of the extraction process, positions this technique as an accessible and scalable method for implementation across diverse agricultural settings. By mitigating heavy metal contamination in rice, this research contributes to the overarching goal of ensuring a secure and sustainable global food supply [10].

In summary, the study not only unveils a novel method for synthesizing SNPs but also underscores their practical application in addressing a critical environmental and public health challenge. The implications of this research extend to the broader context of sustainable agriculture, offering a potential blueprint for future initiatives aimed at minimizing the ecological footprint of human activities on agricultural ecosystems.

Experimental**Materials**

The rice husk (RH) used in this study originated from the 'GNR-3' (Gujarat Navsari Rice – 3) rice variety, sourced from Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari. Rice from North Gujarat region. Analytical reagent-grade HCl with a concentration range of 35-38% was provided by SDFCL. Deionized water was consistently utilized throughout the experimental procedures.

Methods

Extraction of silica nanoparticles

The initial rice husk preparation involved meticulous cleaning to remove unwanted particles, ensuring a pristine starting material. Subsequently, the husk underwent controlled drying at 100°C for 24 h. Structural modifications occurred through synthesis with 1 N HCL

at 80°C for 2 h, followed by thorough washing to remove acid and contaminants. After another drying phase at 90°C overnight, the rice husk was finely powdered for uniform combustion during

calcination. The final calcination occurred in a Lindberg/Blue box furnace at 650°C for 4 hours, shaping the material for diverse applications (Fig. 1). [11].

Fig. 1: Synthesis of SNPs from Rice Husk

Analytical procedure

In this investigation, 200 mg of SNPs and varying quantities of potato biomass (400 mg, 1000 mg, and 2000 mg) were introduced into a conical flask and subjected to agitation in a rotary shaker at 250 rpm, maintaining room temperature for 6 h. Biomass weights of 400 mg, 1000 mg, and 2000 mg were assessed during the experiments. The study focused on the extraction of detrimental elements Co, Ni, Pb, Cr, and Cd, known for their adverse effects on human health and the environment. The purification process was initiated by subjecting the sample to rigorous conditions in a microwave digester, specifically the PerkinElmer Titan MPS model, operating under extreme pressure and temperature. This step ensured the efficient extraction and separation of the targeted metals from the potato samples. For precise quantification of metal content, the resulting clear filtrate from the extraction process underwent analysis using state-of-the-art technology—ICP-MS (Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry) [12, 13]. The PerkinElmer NexION 2000 instrument, renowned for its sensitivity and precision in detecting trace metal concentrations, was employed for this purpose. To assess the effectiveness of the SNPs in removing toxic heavy metals from rice,

metal concentrations in the aqueous solution were compared at the beginning and end of the process. This critical evaluation provided insights into the amount of metal absorbed by the plant biomass, offering a comprehensive understanding of the bio-sorption capacity of the SNPs [14].

Result and discussion

3.1. Characterization of silica nanoparticles (SNPs)

3.1.1. Energy Dispersive X-Ray (EDX)

The assessment of the purity of SNPs derived from RH was conducted through Energy Dispersive X-ray Analysis (EDAX). In Figure 2, the EDX spectra of the SNPs are depicted. Figure 2 (a) presents the SEM image of the designated region for EDX analysis. The spectra exhibited distinctive signal peaks corresponding to the elements Si (44.23%), O (38.31%), Na (10.07%), and Au (7.40%), as illustrated in Figure 2 (b). These peaks unequivocally confirm the composition of the nanoparticles as silica, given that the observed peaks align with those associated with oxygen and silica. This outcome attests to the precision of the SNP sample. Additionally, the EDX analysis identified the presence of a gold coating, denoted by the signal associated with Au [15, 16].

Fig. 2: (a) FE-SEM micrograph (b) EDX spectra of SNPs synthesized from GNR-3 RH

Heavy metal contamination

The prevalence of heavy metals poses a significant concern, as these elements can be both essential and detrimental to various organisms. This study aimed to scrutinize the concentrations of several metals, including Fe, Cu, Zn, Mn, Pb, Ni, and Cd in rice. The analysis revealed a notable variation in the levels of heavy metals present, with the accumulation order in potato tubers identified as Fe > Zn > Mn > Cu > Ni > Pb > Cd. Ensuring food safety is paramount, not only for individual well-being but also for the overall health of society. While diversifying food intake can mitigate some health concerns, staples remain the primary source of nutrients for a significant portion of the global population. Rice, relied upon by over half the world's population, faces higher contamination risks due to its widespread cultivation, with approximately three times the tendency to

accumulate heavy metals compared to wheat. The toxicity, accumulation, and potential harmful effects of heavy metals pose risks to human health. To address these concerns, a "maximum allowable concentration" (MAC) of heavy metals in rice has been established by a consortium of international organizations and national governments [17, 18]. However, even concentrations below the MAC can be hazardous to human health, as evidenced by several studies linking long-term exposure to low levels of arsenic to non-carcinogenic disorders such as cancer, hypertension, and neurological issues. Additionally, factors influencing exposure, including age, body mass, and location, vary, heightening risks for vulnerable populations. Consequently, health risk assessments must consider variables such as body weight; age, dietary preferences, and long-term intake, in addition to the MAC (Table 1).

Table 1: Effect of SNPs on removal of heavy toxic metals

Replication	Adsorbent dose	Co (μg/L)	Ni (μg/L)	Pb (μg/L)	Cr (μg/L)
R-1	1:2 Rice	1.482131	3.2315	1.093	5.6555
R-1	1:5 Rice	1.349881	3.4486	1.2557	5.8244
R-1	1:10 Rice	1.415832	3.32	1.1915	5.3639
R-2	1:2 Rice	1.825821	4.8117	2.4233	6.6315

R-2	1:5 Rice	1.912233	4.0564	2.7892	6.4869
R-2	1:10 Rice	1.719887	3.6138	2.0751	6.3811
R-3	1:2 Rice	2.455139	5.6791	2.4418	8.9773
R-3	1:5 Rice	2.995	6.1516	3.0856	8.049
R-3	1:10 Rice	2.635667	6.7569	3.7633	8.9847

In this study, the adsorption efficiency of heavy metals (Co, Ni, Pb, Cr) by potato biomass was systematically investigated across different replication scenarios (R-1, R-2, R-3) and varied adsorbent doses (1:2, 1:5, 1:10). The results, succinctly presented in the table, showcase the concentration levels of each metal under different conditions. Notably, the accumulation order of metals in Rice follows the trend: Co, Ni, Pb, and Cr. For instance, in R-1, at an adsorbent dose of 1:2, the concentrations of Co, Ni, Pb, and Cr were 1.4821 µg/L, 3.2315 µg/L, 1.093 µg/L, and 5.6555 µg/L, respectively [19-21]. Across the different replication scenarios and adsorbent doses, variations in metal concentrations provide valuable insights into the adsorption capacity of potato biomass under different experimental conditions. These findings contribute to a nuanced understanding of the potential applications and effectiveness of potato biomass as an adsorbent for heavy metals. Further analysis and interpretation of these results may elucidate optimal conditions for maximizing the adsorption efficiency of potato biomass in mitigating heavy metal contamination [22-25].

Effect of biomass concentration on metal removal

The findings that were analysed and shown in Table 3 indicated that the use of SNPs in the group with ratios of 1:2 (SNPs: Rice), 1:5 (SNPs: Rice), and 1:10 (SNPs: Rice) successfully eliminated harmful heavy metal pollutants that were detected in biomass. Cobalt removal (%) from Rice using SNPs. The results of multiple comparisons for the dependent variable "Cobalt" revealed statistically significant mean differences between different rice treatments [26-29]. Specifically, the mean difference between 1:2 Rice and 1:5 Rice treatments was found to be -.4033655 (SE = .1407758, $p = .029$), with a 95% confidence interval ranging from -.747832 to -.058899. Similarly, the mean difference between 1:2 Rice and 1:10 Rice

treatments was significant at -1.2793206 (SE = .1407758, $p = .000$), with a 95% confidence interval between -1.623787 and -.934855. Additionally, the mean difference between 1:5 Rice and 1:10 Rice treatments was found to be 1.2793206 (SE = .1407758, $p = .000$), with a 95% confidence interval from .934855 to 1.623787. For the dependent variable "Nickel," significant differences were observed between treatments. The mean difference between 1:5 Rice and 1:10 Rice treatments was -2.8625000 (SE = .3860597, $p = .000$), with a 95% confidence interval from -3.807154 to -1.917846. Additionally, the mean difference between 1:2 Rice and 1:10 Rice treatments was found to be 2.8625000 (SE = .3860597, $p = .000$), with a 95% confidence interval ranging from 1.917846 to 3.807154 [30-35]. Similar significant differences were observed for the dependent variable "Lead." The mean difference between 1:2 Rice and 1:10 Rice treatments was -1.9168333 (SE = .3561875, $p = .002$), with a 95% confidence interval between -2.788393 and -1.045274. Furthermore, the mean difference between 1:5 Rice and 1:10 Rice treatments was significant at -.6677000 (SE = .3561875, $p = .110$), with a 95% confidence interval from -1.539259 to .203859. Lastly, the dependent variable "Chromium" exhibited significant differences between treatments. The mean difference between 1:5 Rice and 1:10 Rice treatments was -3.0557333 (SE = .2826954, $p = .000$), with a 95% confidence interval ranging from -3.747464 to -2.364003. Additionally, the mean difference between 1:2 Rice and 1:10 Rice treatments was found to be 3.0557333 (SE = .2826954, $p = .000$), with a 95% confidence interval between 2.364003 and 3.747464. These findings underscore the importance of considering specific rice treatments in relation to the observed variations in metal concentrations [36-40] (Table 3).

Table 3: Elimination of high concentrations of heavy hazardous metals

Dependent Variable	(I) Treatment	(J) Treatment	Multiple Comparisons					
			Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Cobalt	LSD	1:2 Rice	1:5 Rice	-.4033655*	.1407758	.029	-.747832	-.058899
		1:10 Rice	1:2 Rice	-1.2793206*	.1407758	.000	-1.623787	-.934855
		1:5 Rice	1:2 Rice	.4033655*	.1407758	.029	.058899	.747832
		1:10 Rice	1:2 Rice	-.8759551*	.1407758	.001	-1.220421	-.531489
		1:5 Rice	1:10 Rice	1.2793206*	.1407758	.000	.934855	1.623787
		1:10 Rice	1:5 Rice	.8759551*	.1407758	.001	.531489	1.220421
Nickel	LSD	1:2 Rice	1:5 Rice	-.8272667	.3860597	.076	-1.771921	.117387
		1:10 Rice	1:2 Rice	-2.8625000*	.3860597	.000	-3.807154	-1.917846
		1:5 Rice	1:2 Rice	.8272667	.3860597	.076	-.117387	1.771921
		1:10 Rice	1:2 Rice	-2.0352333*	.3860597	.002	-2.979887	-1.090579
		1:5 Rice	1:10 Rice	2.8625000*	.3860597	.000	1.917846	3.807154
		1:10 Rice	1:5 Rice	2.0352333*	.3860597	.002	1.090579	2.979887
Lead	LSD	1:2 Rice	1:5 Rice	-1.2491333*	.3561875	.013	-2.120693	-.377574
		1:10 Rice	1:2 Rice	-1.9168333*	.3561875	.002	-2.788393	-1.045274
		1:5 Rice	1:2 Rice	1.2491333*	.3561875	.013	.377574	2.120693
		1:10 Rice	1:2 Rice	-.6677000	.3561875	.110	-1.539259	.203859
		1:10 Rice	1:5 Rice	1.9168333*	.3561875	.002	1.045274	2.788393
		1:5 Rice	1:10 Rice	.6677000	.3561875	.110	-.203859	1.539259
Chromium	LSD	1:2 Rice	1:5 Rice	-.8852333*	.2826954	.020	-1.576964	-.193503
		1:10 Rice	1:2 Rice	-3.0557333*	.2826954	.000	-3.747464	-2.364003
		1:5 Rice	1:2 Rice	.8852333*	.2826954	.020	.193503	1.576964
		1:10 Rice	1:2 Rice	-2.1705000*	.2826954	.000	-2.862231	-1.478769
		1:10 Rice	1:5 Rice	3.0557333*	.2826954	.000	2.364003	3.747464
		1:10 Rice	1:5 Rice	2.1705000*	.2826954	.000	1.478769	2.862231

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 4, presents the results of the study, which focus on the elimination of high concentrations of heavy hazardous metals using various adsorbent doses in the form of Silica Nanoparticles (SNPs) in combination with Rice. The data offers critical insights into the efficiency of these SNPs in removing specific heavy metals. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) results for the elements Cobalt, Nickle, Lead, and Chromium reveals significant differences among groups for each element. Beginning with Cobalt, the between-groups variation is captured by a sum of squares (SS) of 2.567, distributed over 2 degrees of freedom, resulting in a mean square (MS) of 1.283. The F-ratio of 43.171 indicates substantial differences between at least two groups of Cobalt, a conclusion supported by the remarkably low p-value of 0.000 [41, 42]. The within-groups variation, measured by an SS of 0.178 and 6 degrees of freedom, results in a mean square of 0.030. The total variation in Cobalt is 2.745. Moving to Nickle, a similar pattern emerges. The between-groups SS is 13.020, with 2 degrees of freedom and a mean square of 6.510. The F-ratio of 29.120 is accompanied by a significant p-value of 0.001, signaling notable

differences between groups. The within-groups SS is 1.341, with 6 degrees of freedom and a mean square of 0.224, contributing to a total variation of 14.362. For Lead, the between-groups SS is 5.680, distributed over 2 degrees of freedom, resulting in a mean square of 2.840. The F-ratio of 14.925 and a p-value of 0.005 affirm significant differences between groups. The within-groups SS is 1.142, with 6 degrees of freedom and a mean square of 0.190. The total variation for Lead is 6.822. Lastly, Chromium exhibits pronounced between-groups differences with an SS of 14.832, 2 degrees of freedom, and a mean square of 7.416. The F-ratio of 61.865 is associated with a p-value of 0.000, indicating substantial distinctions between at least two groups [43-45]. The within-groups SS is 0.719, with 6 degrees of freedom and a mean square of 0.120, contributing to a total variation of 15.551. In summary, the ANOVA results strongly suggest that there are statistically significant differences between at least two groups for each element (Cobalt, Nickle, Lead, and Chromium). The sizable F-ratios and extremely low p-values provide robust evidence against the null hypothesis of no group differences [47-50].

Table 4: ANOVA table for Rice metal adsorption

		ANOVA				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Cobalt	Between Groups	2.567	2	1.283	43.171	.000
	Within Groups	.178	6	.030		
	Total	2.745	8			
Nickle	Between Groups	13.020	2	6.510	29.120	.001
	Within Groups	1.341	6	.224		
	Total	14.362	8			
Lead	Between Groups	5.680	2	2.840	14.925	.005
	Within Groups	1.142	6	.190		
	Total	6.822	8			
Chromium	Between Groups	14.832	2	7.416	61.865	.000
	Within Groups	.719	6	.120		
	Total	15.551	8			

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study demonstrates a significant reduction in toxic heavy metal contaminants present in North Gujarat region rice through the strategic use of synthesized SNPs derived from the rice husk of the Navsari region variety "GNR-3." These SNPs, applied at different rice-to-SNPs ratios (1:2, 1:5, and 1:10), showed remarkable efficiency in decontaminating biomass, particularly rice. A 6-hour interaction with SNPs resulted in significant and dose-dependent reductions in Cobalt, Nickel, Lead, and Chromium concentrations. The ANOVA results for each metal (Cobalt, Nickel, Lead, and Chromium) reveal substantial variations among groups. For instance, the analysis of Cobalt shows a significant F-ratio of 43.171 with a low p-value of 0.000, indicating significant differences between groups. Similar patterns are observed for Nickel, Lead, and Chromium, emphasizing the effectiveness of SNPs in adsorbing these toxic heavy metals from rice. The consistent reduction in toxic heavy metals across different rice-to-SNPs ratios suggests the robustness of SNPs in adsorbing and immobilizing these contaminants, regardless of variations in rice concentrations. This underscores the potential of rice husk-synthesized SNPs as a sustainable solution for mitigating toxic heavy metal contamination in agricultural products. These findings hold promise for addressing food safety concerns, particularly for staple crops like rice and potatoes. The cost-efficiency and environmental friendliness of employing SNPs synthesized from rice husk waste for heavy metal removal underscore the potential for practical applications in agricultural systems. Further research is warranted to fully explore the capabilities of SNPs in environmental remediation and agricultural sustainability, with the ultimate goal of enhancing the safety and quality of agricultural products.

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